
Actuating English Language Learning through Information and Communication Technologies and Podcasts

(Short Communication)

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Discussion

Communication improves our experience and shapes thought-process. The process of exchanging information taking wide varieties of forms through a common system of symbols, facilitating interaction among people is known as communication. In the present scenario, a wide range of skills are required by engineering graduates to lead the professional world. Development of technical knowledge and skills has been the prime motive of conventional engineering curriculum but today both written and spoken communication skills are the primary assets for the professionals to get engaged with other professional groups. It is a fundamental attribute of cultural identity and empowerment. Effectiveness and efficiency in communication are a must for supervising work, co-ordinating various functions and people and developing products and relations. It gives a modest touch to scroll the major issues and concerns, theories and principles, characteristics and constituents, needs and significance besides the role of learners, engineers, tools and techniques in making the communicative language teaching-learning effective and successful as an approach.

Today's education system has adopted podcasting as an instructional tool used extensively by the learners as an artefact and evidence of learning. Actually, a podcast is typically an audio file that is downloaded and listened to. People generally produce podcasts to share ideas, presentations, or music. It is an emerging method that reinforces particular tasks, promotes different activities

and also supports an independent learning as an alternative approach to teaching and learning process. Usually podcasts are linked from a blog, so "podcasting" is often used to denote audio-blogging. Podcasting as a tool, allows the teachers to share their ideas and suggestions in order to improve their approaches of teaching. It is useful for recording a teacher's lesson and a student's conversation or both. It plays a very important role in academics, which can be later seen as a development of [Rapid E-Learning](#) as the content, through podcasting can be created swiftly and without much effort.

The new digital technologies have permeated economy, politics, workplaces, the ways we communicate with each other as well as operation of all levels of education from kindergarten to doctoral studies. Learning is using technology to deliver training anytime, anywhere where the learners receive the content at real time or the learners can pace their own learning. Utilizing the internet to deliver e-learning initiatives has created expectations both in business market and in higher education institutions. This idea of engaging with people through technology is cost effective. E-Learning is an adaptive learning method which is learner centered and also promotes social and collaborative learning. It provides a way to better management of large group of students, while maintaining increased retention and a stronger grasp on the subject. Its major role is to provide greater flexibility of access.

Communication technologies are generally categorized as asynchronous or synchronous. Asynchronous activities use technologies such as blogs, wikis, and discussion boards. Synchronous activities involve the exchange of ideas and information with one or more participants during the same period of time. Learning management system and learning content management system is software used for delivering tracking the managing training education Luskin says that the "e" should be interpreted to mean exciting, energetic, enthusiastic, emotional, extended, excellent, and educational in addition to "electronic" that is a traditional national interpretation. This broader interpretation allows for 21st century applications for the improvement of Higher Education. Rapid changes in the technologies are indicating that the role of E-learning in future will grow tremendously in education.

As an emerging trend, Podcasting is considered as a medium which allows students to use technologies based on entertainment systems such as portable audio players (e.g. an iPod) for educational experiences. Podcasts emerge to proffer convenient professional development and opportunities to the teachers which can give them later the freedom to select what, when and where they want to learn with an objective to make their teaching-learning more interesting and output-oriented. The institutions can use podcasts to make announcements via their Web site. Instead of making viewers come to the website that houses, the content can be updated whenever they want, users could count on the receiver to do it instead-tracking all the podcast feeds they liked and automatically saving them to the computer. These include a hands-on and reflective approach to copyright and fair use in creating digital media.

The objective of the present article is to discuss about the benefits, uses and the application of ICTs and podcast for educational advancement which would definitely endow with a support in relation to core teaching-learning materials. In addition to this, this paper is an attempt to explore how we can actuate communication skills through Information and Communication Technologies (**ICTs**) **and Podcasts** more flexible and reachable to the last person of our social strata in the 21st century.

Keywords: E-Learning, Technology, Education, Retention, Social welfare.